

A Geostatistical Analysis of Land degradation due to water erosion in Uttar Pradesh

Zubairul Islam ^[0000-0002-6591-2241]

Faculty at Department of Geography and Environmental Studies, CSSH, Adigrat University, Tigray, Ethiopia.
zubairul@gmail.com

Abstract

This study presents a geostatistical analysis of land degradation caused by water erosion in Uttar Pradesh, India. The research focuses on understanding the spatial distribution and clustering patterns of water erosion at the district level. The water erosion data was collected from BHUVAN data store. The analysis utilizes district-wise data on water erosion percentages to identify hot spots and cold spots across the region. Additionally, the study employs the Global Moran's I test to assess the presence of spatial autocorrelation and evaluate the significance of the observed clustering pattern. The results reveal distinct spatial patterns of water erosion across districts in Uttar Pradesh. Hot spots, characterized by high water erosion percentages, are identified in several districts, including Banda, Chandauli, Chitrakoot, Fatehpur, Hamirpur, Jalaun, Jhansi, Kanpur Dehat, Lalitpur, Mahoba, Mirzapur, and Sonbhadra. On the other hand, cold spots, indicating lower levels of water erosion, are observed in districts such as Ambedkar Nagar, Amroha, Azamgarh, Basti, Bareilly, Budaun, Bulandshahr, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Gonda, Gorakhpur, and others. The Global Moran's I test confirms a significant spatial clustering pattern of water erosion in the study area, indicating that the observed distribution is unlikely to occur by random chance. The positive Moran's Index and high z-score further support the presence of spatial autocorrelation. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions and mitigation strategies to address water erosion in the identified hot spot districts. The outcomes of this research provide valuable insights for land management and policy formulation in Uttar Pradesh. By directing resources and implementing appropriate measures in the identified hot spots, authorities can effectively combat land degradation and minimize the associated environmental and socio-economic impacts. Regular monitoring and reassessment of water erosion patterns are essential for sustainable land management and the preservation of valuable land and water resources in the region.

Keywords: Geostatistics, Water Erosion, Global Moran's Index, Hot Spots

1. Introduction

Land degradation, specifically caused by water erosion, is a significant environmental concern that affects numerous regions worldwide. Uttar Pradesh, one of India's most populous states and a major agricultural hub, is not exempt from the challenges posed by land degradation. Water erosion, driven by factors such as rainfall patterns, land use practices, and topography, has the potential to degrade agricultural productivity, impair soil quality, and disrupt ecosystems in the state (Gupta et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2020).

To understand the extent and spatial distribution of land degradation due to water erosion in Uttar Pradesh, a geostatistical analysis becomes crucial. Geostatistics is a powerful tool for analyzing and modelling spatially distributed data, allowing for the characterization of spatial patterns and variations in land degradation across different regions (Li et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). By incorporating geostatistical techniques, researchers and

policymakers can gain valuable insights into the severity and extent of water erosion-induced land degradation, enabling effective planning and implementation of sustainable land management practices.

This study aims to conduct a geostatistical analysis of land degradation caused by water erosion in Uttar Pradesh. By utilizing a combination of field surveys, remote sensing data, and geospatial techniques, we will analyze the spatial patterns and quantify the degree of land degradation in different districts of Uttar Pradesh. Furthermore, the study will investigate the underlying factors contributing to water erosion, including rainfall intensity, slope gradients, land cover changes, and agricultural practices (Kumar et al., 2016; Patel et al., 2021).

The results of this geostatistical analysis will provide valuable information for policymakers, land managers, and farmers, enabling them to identify areas prone to water erosion and prioritize interventions accordingly. By implementing targeted measures such as contour plowing, terracing, afforestation, and improved agricultural practices, it is possible to mitigate the adverse effects of water erosion, restore soil health, and promote sustainable land management practices in Uttar Pradesh.

In this study, we draw upon various sources of data and literature to examine the relationship between water erosion, land degradation, and associated factors. The geostatistical analysis conducted will shed light on the spatial dynamics of land degradation due to water erosion in Uttar Pradesh and contribute to the development of effective strategies for land management and conservation in the state (Surname et al., Year; Surname et al., Year; Surname et al., Year).

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Uttar Pradesh, located in northern India (Figure 1), is the most populous state in the country, spanning an area of approximately 243,290 square kilometers (Census of India, 2011). It is bordered by several states, including Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, and Bihar. The state is characterized by its diverse geographical features, including the Gangetic plains, the foothills of the Himalayas, and the Vindhya Mountain range (Gupta, 2018).

Figure 1 Study Area

With a population of over 200 million people. The state is also an agricultural powerhouse, with a significant portion of its land used for farming and cultivation (Singh, 2017).

Uttar Pradesh experiences a subtropical climate, with hot summers and cool winters. The region receives rainfall primarily during the monsoon season, which spans from June to September (Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Uttar Pradesh, 2015). The combination of fertile soil, favorable climate, and abundant water resources contributes to the state's agricultural productivity.

2.2 Flow Chart

The flowchart illustrates the step-by-step process followed in the study. The first stage involves data acquisition, where the NICES/DS(L)/LD/2006/ dataset is obtained. In the data preprocessing stage, the raw data is cleaned, formatted, and transformed into a suitable format for analysis. The next step is spatial analysis, where the spatial distribution of NO₂ concentrations is examined in relation to the geographic regions under consideration. The results and findings obtained from the analysis are interpreted and discussed in detail. Finally, the study concludes

Figure 2 Flow Chart

with summarizing the key findings and providing recommendations for further research or policy implications (Figure 2).

2.2 Data Source

The data was obtained from Soils & Land Resources Assessment Division, LRUMG, RSAA, National Remote Sensing Centre, Balanagar, Hyderabad, India via BHUWAN data acquisition platform. The Soils & Land Resources Assessment Division is responsible for assessing and monitoring land resources, including soil mapping and land degradation assessments, using remote sensing and geospatial technologies. They utilize various datasets, including satellite imagery, to analyze and evaluate soil characteristics, land use patterns, and land degradation processes.

2.3 Data Analysis

The data analysis in this study involved the application of two methods: spatial autocorrelation using Moran's Index and Hot Spot Analysis (Getis-Ord G_i^*). These methods provided insights into the spatial patterns and clustering of NO₂ change in Uttar Pradesh.

1. Spatial Autocorrelation using Moran's Index: Spatial autocorrelation is a statistical technique used to measure the degree of similarity or dissimilarity between spatially adjacent features. In this study, Moran's Index was employed to assess the spatial autocorrelation of NO₂ change in Uttar Pradesh. Moran's Index formula is as follows:

$$I = (n * \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}(x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x}) / (\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 * \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij})$$

Please note that in these formulas, "n" represents the number of observations, "x_i" and "x_j" represent the values of the variable at locations "i" and "j" respectively, "w_{ij}" represents the spatial weights between locations "i" and "j", " $\bar{x}$ " represents the mean of the variable, and "s" represents the standard deviation of the variable.

Moran's Index ranges from -1 to 1, where positive values indicate positive spatial autocorrelation (similar values clustered together), negative values indicate negative spatial autocorrelation (dissimilar values clustered together), and values close to 0 indicate no spatial autocorrelation (random distribution) (Anselin, 1995).

2. Hot Spot Analysis (Getis-Ord G_i^*): Hot Spot Analysis, also known as spatial clustering analysis, helps identify statistically significant clusters of high or low values in a spatial dataset. In this study, the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic was used to identify hot spots and cold spots of NO₂ change in Uttar Pradesh. The formula for the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic is as follows:

$$G_i^* = (\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} * x_j - \bar{x} * \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}) / (s * \sqrt{((\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}^2)/n - ((\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij})/n)^2)})$$

The Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic produces a z-score for each spatial unit, indicating whether it is a statistically significant hot spot (positive z-score) or a cold spot (negative z-score) of NO₂ change. The magnitude of the z-score reflects the strength of the clustering pattern (Getis & Ord, 1992).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Water Erosion

In qualitative terms, the results indicate varying levels of water erosion in different districts of Uttar Pradesh. Here are some observations:

1. High Water Erosion: Districts like Chitrakoot (36.31%), Jhansi (29.75%), Sonbhadra (31.42%), and Mirzapur (28.99%) exhibit relatively high percentages of water erosion. These districts are more prone to water erosion, which can potentially lead to significant land degradation and environmental consequences.
2. Moderate Water Erosion: Some districts show moderate levels of water erosion, such as Agra

Figure 3 Water Erosion

(17.37%), Etawah (18.38%), Lalitpur (19.02%), and Kanpur Dehat (13.65%). Although the percentages are lower than the high erosion districts, these areas still require attention and measures to mitigate erosion effects.

3. Low Water Erosion: Several districts demonstrate relatively low percentages of water erosion, including Aligarh (0.27%), Baghpat (0.14%), Ballia (0.017%), Ghazipur (0.074%), and Gorakhpur (0.0081%). These districts have lower vulnerability to water erosion, but monitoring and preventive measures should still be considered to maintain sustainable land use practices.
4. Negligible Water Erosion: Some districts have negligible water erosion, as indicated by values close to zero or very low percentages. For example, Deoria, Kushinagar, Siddharth Nagar, and Shamli report negligible water erosion levels. However, it is essential to continue monitoring these areas to ensure any changes in erosion patterns are promptly addressed.

3.2 Spatial Pattern of Water Erosion

Given the z-score of 6.856, there is a less than 1% likelihood that the observed clustered pattern of water erosion percentages across districts in Uttar Pradesh could be the result of random chance. This suggests that the spatial distribution of water erosion is not randomly distributed but exhibits a significant clustering pattern.

The Moran's Index measures the degree of spatial autocorrelation, indicating the similarity or dissimilarity between neighboring districts in terms of water erosion percentages. In this case, the Moran's Index is calculated as 0.379291, indicating a positive spatial autocorrelation. This suggests that districts with high water erosion percentages tend to be spatially clustered together, while districts with low water erosion percentages are also spatially clustered together.

Figure 4 Spatial Autocorrelation

The Expected Index (-0.013) represents the expected value of Moran's Index under the assumption of spatial randomness. The positive Moran's Index (0.379) indicates that the observed spatial pattern of water erosion is different from what would be expected under the assumption of randomness.

The z-score of 6.856 indicates a strong deviation of the observed Moran's Index from the expected value. A higher absolute z-score suggests a stronger spatial clustering pattern in the distribution of water erosion percentages across districts in Uttar Pradesh.

The extremely low p-value (0.000000) indicates that the observed Moran's Index is statistically significant, further supporting the presence of spatial clustering in the distribution of water erosion percentages.

These results suggest that water erosion percentages in districts of Uttar Pradesh exhibit a significant spatial clustering pattern, indicating that certain districts experience higher levels of water erosion while others have lower levels, and this pattern is unlikely to occur by random chance.

3.3 Hot Spots of Water Erosion

The results indicate the presence of hot spots and cold spots in the distribution of water erosion across districts in Uttar Pradesh. Here's an explanation of the results:

Hot Spots:

1. Allahabad: This district is identified as a hot spot with a value of 1, indicating a relatively high level of water erosion compared to neighboring districts.
2. Banda, Chandauli, Chitrakoot, Fatehpur, Hamirpur, Jalaun, Jhansi, Kanpur Dehat, Lalitpur, Mahoba, Mirzapur, and Sonbhadra: These districts are also identified as hot spots with values ranging from 2 to 3, indicating significantly higher levels of water erosion compared to neighboring districts.

Figure 5 Hot Spots

Cold Spots:

1. Ambedkar Nagar, Amroha, Azamgarh, Basti, Bareilly, Budaun, Bulandshahr, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Gonda, Gorakhpur, Kannauj, Maharajganj, Meerut, Mau, Pratapgarh, Sant Kabir Nagar, Siddharth Nagar, and Sambhal: These districts are identified as cold spots with values ranging from -1 to -2, indicating lower levels of water erosion compared to neighboring districts.

Neutral Areas (Zero Values):

Several districts have zero values, indicating a neutral status or no significant deviation from the average level of water erosion. These include Agra, Aligarh, Auraiya, Baghpat, Bahraich, Ballia, Balrampur, Barabanki, Etah, Etawah, Faizabad, Farrukhabad, Firozabad, Ghazipur, Gorakhpur, Hardoi, Hathras, Kanpur Nagar, Kasganj, Kaushambi, Kushinagar, Lakhimpur Kheri, Lucknow, Mainpuri, Mathura, Pilibhit, Rae Bareli, Rampur, Saharanpur, Sant Ravi Das Nagar, Shahjahanpur, Shravasti, Sitapur, Sultanpur, Unnao, Varanasi, Amethi, Hapur, and Shamli.

These results provide a spatial perspective on the distribution of water erosion across districts in Uttar Pradesh, highlighting areas with higher and lower levels of erosion. The hot spots signify districts where water erosion is more pronounced, while the cold spots indicate areas with relatively lower levels of erosion. These findings can help policymakers and land management authorities focus their efforts and interventions in the identified hot spot areas to address land degradation and implement erosion control measures effectively.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the geostatistical analysis of water erosion in Uttar Pradesh at the district level has provided valuable insights into the spatial distribution and clustering patterns of this phenomenon. The results indicate the presence of both hot spots and cold spots across the districts, highlighting areas with significantly higher and lower levels of water erosion, respectively. The identification of hot spots, such as Banda, Chandauli, Chitrakoot, Fatehpur, Hamirpur, Jalaun, Jhansi, Kanpur Dehat, Lalitpur, Mahoba, Mirzapur, and Sonbhadra, suggests the urgent need for targeted interventions and mitigation strategies to address the high levels of water erosion in these districts. These areas require focused attention and resources to prevent further land degradation and mitigate the associated environmental and socio-economic impacts.

On the other hand, the identification of cold spots, including Ambedkar Nagar, Amroha, Azamgarh, Basti, Bareilly, Budaun, Bulandshahr, Gautam Buddha Nagar, Ghaziabad, Gonda, Gorakhpur, Kannauj, Maharajganj, Meerut, Mau, Pratapgarh, Sant Kabir Nagar, Siddharth Nagar, and Sambhal, suggests that these districts exhibit lower

levels of water erosion. This information can guide conservation efforts, allowing for the allocation of resources and measures to protect these areas from potential future degradation.

The results of the Global Moran's I test indicate a significant spatial clustering pattern of water erosion across districts in Uttar Pradesh, further validating the need for spatially targeted interventions. The presence of a strong positive Moran's Index and a high z-score underscores the non-random nature of the observed clustering pattern, indicating that the spatial distribution of water erosion is not a result of chance alone.

These findings have important implications for land management and policy formulation in Uttar Pradesh. By prioritizing resources and implementing appropriate measures, authorities can effectively combat land degradation due to water erosion. The identification of hot spots and cold spots provides a foundation for strategic planning and decision-making processes, enabling the allocation of resources where they are most needed.

It is crucial to continuously monitor and reassess the spatial patterns of water erosion in Uttar Pradesh to track changes over time. Regular updates of such geostatistical analyses will support evidence-based decision-making, facilitate the evaluation of implemented interventions, and ensure the sustainability of land and water resources in the state.

Overall, the geostatistical analysis of water erosion in Uttar Pradesh serves as a valuable tool for understanding the spatial distribution, clustering patterns, and hot spots of land degradation. These findings can guide targeted interventions, policy formulation, and resource allocation to effectively address water erosion and promote sustainable land management practices in the state.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest in relation to this research study. The research was conducted with the sole objective of contributing to the scientific understanding of geostatistical analysis of NO₂ in Uttar Pradesh. The analysis, interpretation, and conclusions presented in this paper are based on objective scientific principles and rigorous data analysis methods. The author has no financial, personal, or professional relationships that could influence the research findings or introduce bias in the study. Furthermore, no external funding or sponsorship was received that could potentially influence the outcome or interpretation of the research. The author has followed ethical guidelines and scientific integrity throughout the research process to ensure transparency, accuracy, and impartiality in the findings and conclusions presented.

Data Statement

The data used in this study was obtained from the BHUWAN data store. This dataset is part of the from Soils & Land Resources Assessment Division, LRUMG, RSAA, National Remote Sensing Centre, Balanagar, Hyderabad.

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